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NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER
ANNUAL REPORT 2011

DIRECTOR'S MESSAGE

In the last Annual Report, I noted that NESCent was in fine shape; nonetheless, I ended my message by saying that in 2011, I would focus on two areas where closer attention is warranted: improving the participation of underrepresented minorities in evolutionary science, and securing the long-term future of NESCent beyond the limits of NSF funding.

This year, I can again report that NESCent remains in good health, with a vigorous and expanded science program that includes new targeted activities, outreach that has reached out beyond demographic, disciplinary and geographic borders, and an informatics team that has shown, by example, the benefits that accrue when IT is closely associated with the science it supports.

As for underrepresented minorities at NESCent, and in evolutionary science, we spent a great deal of time trying to identify what can be done to effect greater participation. NESCent already supports the travel of MSI faculty and students to the Evolution conference, and we run (with Scott Edwards, at Harvard) a program that mentors underrepresented undergraduate students at the meeting. NESCent is also a sponsor of SACNAS, where we organize several activities. On reflection, we recognize that a major challenge that relates to the representation of underrepresented minorities in the evolutionary sciences is one of recruitment – in short, very few students (underrepresented or otherwise) think of evolutionary biology as a career option.

This year, in an effort to counter this lack of awareness, we introduced a new targeted activity, specifically, a call to develop programs that will demonstrate the value of evolutionary science to underrepresented minorities in K-12 classrooms. We hope that by targeting the educational pipeline at a relatively early stage, students will appreciate that successful and stimulating careers are not the province of the professions alone.

NESCent's future – this is an ongoing topic of discussion at NESCent, whether it is around a conference table, at lunch, or in the corridor outside my office. We spent a great deal of time with the Oversight Committee, Operations Committee, Advisory Board, and amongst the directors and management team, thinking about how we

should approach the Center's sustainability. What does it mean to keep "NESCent" going? If we lose or change certain programs, is it still "NESCent"? And if we keep all our existing programs, should we do so at the cost of the breadth of science that NESCent presently supports? These, and a host of other questions, have brought the question of sustainability and NESCent's future into sharper focus. Our

discussions have reached a point where we think we can develop a business plan based around 2 or 3 realistic scenarios. This in itself gives us cause for cautious optimism – if the pathway to sustainability is not guaranteed, at least we can see what the likely pathways might be, and we (along with our stakeholders) can begin to make plans.

In 2012, we will continue our focus on sustainability. By the end of that year, we will have a better idea of NESCent's future, and we will begin, if necessary, to develop a transition plan.

Allen Rodrigo :: 26 September 2011

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77,000 visitors from
176
countries
visited the NESCent website

\$22,777,000
additional grant support
obtained by scientists
since 2007 as a direct
result of their involvement
with **NESCent**

MORE THAN 65
articles on NESCent
science appeared in the
mainstream
media including

Science Magazine
NPR • Scientific American
Discovery Channel
WIRED • The New York Times
Time Magazine

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In 2011, NESCent continued to expand its programs, introducing new activities (e.g., the Darwin Day Roadshow and the Evolution Film Festival, and a journalist-in-residence program), and bringing to fruition activities that were initiated in 2010 (e.g., the NESCent Ambassador Program and the NESCent Academy, as well as cross-center meetings for postdoctoral fellows and for cyberinfrastructure). The NESCent Oversight Committee met for the first time, bringing together senior administrators from the partner institutions. The focus at that meeting – and indeed, at NESCent for most of this year – was NESCent's future after NSF funding ceases in 2014. Of relevance to these discussions is the fact that NESCent continues to enjoy the evolutionary science community's endorsement. Likewise, the partner institutions recognize that sustaining NESCent is important. For its part, NESCent has stepped up its engagement with the partner institutions, capitalizing on the skills and collaborative networks of faculty at these institutions. In an effort to develop a strategy for sustainability, NESCent is developing a business plan for review in the first quarter of 2012 by the Oversight Committee.

This year saw a few staff changes, with Phillip Grosshans joining NESCent as our new Assistant Director for Administration. Todd Vision began his sabbatical in the second half of 2011, and Joel Kingsolver presently acts as the Associate Director of Informatics. Other staff losses, particularly in IT, have been challenging, and we expect that this situation will not improve as we head towards 2014.

Recognizing that 2014 is going to be a watershed year for NESCent, we move into 2012 preparing to deal with transition, and equip staff with skills to compete in the workforce.

NESCent's visibility within the broader evolutionary science community continues to grow. In 2011, we had more than 77,000 visitors from 176 countries to our website (up from 66,000 visitors from 54 countries last year). Also, in 2011, more than 65 news articles on NESCent science appeared in the mainstream media, including *Science Magazine*, *NPR*, *Scientific American*, *Discovery Channel*, *Wired*, *The New York Times*, and *TIME Magazine* (up from 40 news articles for last year). In September 2011, NESCent also launched its new website.

This year, NESCent submits a proposal to host the 2014 Joint Annual Meeting of the Society for the Study of Evolution, the Society for Systematic Biology, and the American Society of Naturalists (Evolution 2014). The plan is to hold the meeting at the Raleigh Convention Center in June 2014. NESCent is working with an organizing committee drawn from faculty at Duke University, UNC-Chapel Hill, NCSU, UNC-Greensboro, and East Carolina University. If NESCent's proposal is accepted, it will provide an opportunity to celebrate 10 years of synthetic evolutionary science, and acknowledge the support that the evolutionary science community has given to the Center.

Transforming evolutionary science...

SCIENCE & SYNTHESIS

NESCent's Science program in Year 7 expanded, particularly with the addition of targeted activities:

Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings. We received 10 Working Group proposals and 17 Catalysis Meeting proposals in 2011. Of these, 9 Catalysis Meetings and 5 Working Groups were approved by the board.

Long term sabbaticals. We received 14 requests for year long sabbaticals at the Center this year, double the number from last year. Three scholars are already in residence and 1 more was awarded in the current round.

Postdoctoral Fellowships. We received 27 applications for Postdoctoral Fellowships; 8 were awarded and 6 were accepted. These scholars join the current set of Postdoctoral Fellows for a total of 15 — our largest group of Postdoctoral Fellows so far.

Graduate Fellowships. Growth of our Graduate Fellowship program continues this year; we currently have three Graduate Fellows

pursuing a range of research projects. An additional four proposals are now being considered.

NESCent has hosted nearly 4200 visitors from more than 51 countries

Targeted Research Areas. Four targeted initiatives are currently underway to jumpstart new areas of evolutionary synthesis:

Astrobiology, Evolutionary Medicine, Evolution and the Social Sciences, and K-12 Evolution Education for Underrepresented Minorities.

Our open call for development of evolutionary medicine curricula drew 5 proposals, two of which were supported. Our targeted initiative on Evolution and the Social Sciences also drew 5 proposals, currently under consideration.

Postdoctoral Symposium. On April 17-20, NESCent held the first annual Joint Synthesis Center Postdoctoral Symposium for postdoctoral fellows from many of the synthesis

centers. The three-day symposium included a combination of brief research presentations by the postdocs, professional development activities, and breakout sessions on topics chosen by the fellows. Postdoctoral fellows were attracted from a broad assortment of centers and disciplinary backgrounds (9 centers and 31 fellows).

*Removing barriers
to accessing,
sharing, and
interpreting data*

INFORMATICS

NESCent's Informatics activities are driven both by the informatics needs of visiting and resident scientists, and by our commitment to remove common informatics-related barriers to synthetic research. Our major accomplishments for Year 7 include the following:

Sponsored science informatics support infrastructure. NESCent held a workshop on "Cyberinfrastructure for Collaborative Science," which brought together informatics personnel from seven synthesis centers, leaders of successful cyberinfrastructure projects, and social scientists investigating the socio-technical aspects of cyberinfrastructure for scientific collaboration. After reviewing the suite of informatics technologies and services provided to sponsored scientists, the workshop participants identified several key areas for consolidating existing work towards best-of-breed reusable solutions, including file sharing and collaborative curation of data matrices.

Sharing, reusability, and interoperability of data. NESCent co-organized and held a hackathon on enhancing the tools available for evolutionary analysis within the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD). The Dryad data repository can now hand-shake with the community resource TreeBASE. Dryad's adoption has been steadily increasing, as evidenced by the rate of new depositions as well as the diversity of journals in which the corresponding articles were published. The Joint Data Archiving Policy (JDAP) went into effect in January 2011. An NSF grant application was awarded on scaling up the methods and knowledgebase developed in the Phenoscope project for integrating phenotype observations from different fields. NESCent personnel lead the assembly of a collaborative NSF grant proposal that aims to make archival and synthesis of published phylogenetic knowledge significantly more scalable and rewarding to authors.

Stepped-up human capacity building. As part of the NESCent Academy, NESCent sponsored four short courses in evolutionary informatics, on topics ranging from practical programming skills, to statistical data analysis, to distributing computationally-intensive jobs using cloud computing (for further details see the section on the NESCent Academy). NESCent organized ten summer internship opportunities, eight of which were through the Google Summer of Code program, and two of which were funded through the Data Observation Network for Earth (DataONE). NESCent also sponsored and co-organized the second annual iEvoBio conference on collaborative open-source software development in evolution and biodiversity, which was similarly successful as the inaugural conference, and also featured new elements.

In Year 8, our activities will emphasize the following areas:
First, we will complement our informatics course program with shorter, focused hands-on training activities that are responsive to the informatics training needs of resident and visiting scholars.
Second, we will subject user-interfaces of custom applications under active development to review targeted at improving usability and user-experience.
Third, we will continue to play a leading role in the evolutionary science community in promoting standards and infrastructure for online discovery, access, and reuse of data. Specifically, this will include improving the discoverability, interoperability, documentation, and packaging of data compiled under NESCent sponsorship.
Fourth, we will develop a comprehensive strategy for how the Center's Informatics products can best be sustained, or kept available, beyond the expiration of NSF support for the Center in 2014.

EDUCATION AND OUTREACH

NESCent's Year 7 Education and Outreach activities saw the introduction of a number of successful new initiatives, along with the continuation of established programs and partnerships. Over the last several years, NESCent's Education and Outreach efforts have been built on five pillars:

Outreach to the Education Community

This includes established programs such as the annual NABT Evolution Symposium and teacher workshops, and new programs such as the Darwin Day Roadshow project and NESCent's Evolution Film Festival.

Outreach to the General Public This includes our established Darwin Day efforts, other sponsored talks and events for the public, and new programs such as the Darwin Day Roadshow.

Outreach to Underrepresented Minorities This includes our annual SACNAS activities, several different travel award/scholarship programs, and new programs such as our targeted initiative in K-12

evolution education for underrepresented minorities, and our after-school science project, Seeing and Learning Science After School (SALSA).

Each year, NESCent celebrates Charles Darwin's birthday with a day-long outreach event in partnership with the North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences.

Outreach to International Science and Education Communities The cornerstone of these efforts is our recently launched NESCent Ambassador program, for which we received funding in the past year, and which will continue to expand in the coming year.

"Inreach" to the Science Community These efforts have coalesced in the past year with the hiring of a Training Manager, and with the establishment of the NESCent Academy as an umbrella under which all short courses/workshops and training opportunities are housed.

In the coming year, we will build on the five pillars of NESCent Education and Outreach by maintaining our collection of existing piloting, developing and exploring new opportunities.

ASSESSMENT

NESCent's Assessment program continues to mature. In 2011, we developed a cohesive assessment program across our three divisions. This includes both developing an assessment strategy for our current 5-year cycle and identifying specific data and analyses to meet our assessment objectives. Results from NESCent's self-assessment show that:

- Since the center's inception the total number of visitors continues to grow with no signal of leveling or diminishing. Annually, ~54% of participants in NESCent activities are new to the center and represented 50 countries.
- NESCent programs on average have 30% female representation both in terms of PIs and participants, which is higher than current NSF estimates of women with PhDs practicing in biology.
- NESCent publications covered approximately three times as many subject categories as comparison groups.
- NESCent papers contain on average a greater number of authors and affiliations than comparison groups.

- As measured by number of authors, departments, departmental types, etc., NESCent Postdoctoral Fellows are more collaborative.
- Working groups that incorporate a greater percentage of minorities and emerging scientists are more productive.
- Since 2007, scientists have obtained more than \$22,777,000 in additional grant support as a direct result of their involvement with NESCent-supported programs.
- NESCent has a high per paper citation rate, and a low percentage of uncited papers, compared to most universities.
- In Year 7, NESCent's h-index rose from 26 to 32 and our papers have garnered an additional 1,116 citations for a cumulative total of 4,711 (an average of 16.13 citations per item).
- NESCent publications have occurred 685 times on blogs registered by Google, 246 times in CiteULike, 3,563 times in Mendeley, and 217 times in Regtranbase.

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HIGHLIGHTS

As in previous years, there has been no shortage of innovative and exciting work at NESCent. Here are just a few highlights from our Science, Informatics and Education/Outreach portfolios, illustrating the breadth of activity at the Center:

Integrating Multiple Datasets and Developing New Analytical Tools to Uncover Phenotypic Correlations Across the Whole Organism

NESCent postdoctoral fellow Juan Santos published a paper in the March 29, 2011 issue of the journal *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science* titled “Phenotypic integration emerges from aposematism and scale in poison frogs.” Santos was able to integrate structural equation models with phylogenetic correlations to gain insights into how phenotypic traits in poison frogs are correlated. The paper reports that the most boldly-colored and bad-tasting frogs are also the most physically fit. This reflects that poisonous frogs spend a considerable amount of time foraging for toxin-containing food needed for poison. *Futurity*, *Live Science*, *MSNBC*, *Wired*, and *Animal Planet* covered Juan’s paper.

In 2011, NESCent took Darwin Day on the road, traveling to multiple locations around the country to share our scientists’ expertise and enthusiasm for the study of evolution.

Repurposing Legacy Data to Address Outstanding Questions on Life History Strategies

NESCent postdoctoral fellow Josh Auld published a paper in the Jan 12, 2011 issue of *Oikos* titled “Life history of breeding partners alters age-related changes of reproductive traits in a natural population of blue tits.” Analyzing lifetime data for nearly 600 female and 600 male blue tits collected from 1979 to 2007, Auld found that how fast a female’s fertility fades with age depends partly on her partners. Specifically, he found that fertility declines less quickly for females whose mates become first-time fathers young, potentially because these males are healthier or more experienced. *MSNBC* and *USA Today* covered Josh’s paper.

Mammalian Feeding Experiments End-user Database (FEED) We had previously created a proof-of-concept application (FEED) for

the working group on “Analysis and Synthesis of Physiologic Data from the Mammalian Feeding Apparatus,” with the goal of enabling comparative analysis of data on craniofacial and neuromuscular motor function across mammalian species. In Year 7, we developed this application into a fully functional prototype (see <http://feedexp.org>) that working group PIs demonstrated at a dedicated symposium at the annual conference of the Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology (SICB). This prototype was subsequently the subject of the lead publication in an invited special issue of the society’s journal (ICB). An NSF ABI proposal submitted by the PIs in 2010 has now been funded. The new grant will support the development of this database into a community resource that preserves decades of experimental data on the physiology and functional morphology of feeding in mammals, and makes them available for future comparative analysis. The proposed work also harnesses the Center’s expertise and cyberinfrastructure initiatives to link these physiologic data to appropriate anatomy, phenotype, and physiologic function ontologies. These accomplishments exemplify the progression from working group support product to science-driven enhanced community resource that the Center’s informatics efforts and diverse expertise can enable.

The Darwin Day Roadshow

This highly successful program sent seven NESCent scientists to K-12 schools, museums and community centers in small, rural communities in four states (Iowa, Montana, Nebraska and Virginia). The goal was to deliver Darwin Day presentations to audiences who would not otherwise have exposure to evolutionary science and scientists. This not only benefited students and other members of the communities that we visited, but provided powerful professional development opportunities for the NESCent scientists, who described the experience as “life changing.” This program will continue in 2012 with additional scientists visiting new states around the country. More information about the Darwin Day Roadshow can be found at roadshow.nescent.org.

NESCent Evolution Film Festival NESCent introduced a fun and wildly successful program this year by launching a film festival/video contest at the Evolution 2011 conference in Oklahoma City, OK. Scientists and filmmakers around the world were encouraged to describe an interesting aspect of evolution (their own research or anything else of interest) in a three-minute video. Nearly 20 videos were submitted and 13 were screened during the festival. The capacity crowd voted on their favorites and the winners were announced at the conference’s final banquet. All of the video entries are now housed on the NESCent website, where they serve as tremendous evolution education resources for K-12 and undergraduate students, and the general public. Based, in part, on multiple requests from throughout the evolution community, this program will be continued at future Evolution conferences. For more about the film festival, please see <http://filmfestival.nescent.org>.

Cyberinfrastructure for Collaborative Science Workshop

The heterogeneous, multi-disciplinary research collaborations facilitated by science centers in general and synthesis centers in particular often rely heavily on informatics to succeed. Even though each center is unique with respect to its audience, mission, and resources, the centers invariably encounter similar technical and sociological challenges in supporting these informatics needs. Yet, the informatics personnel at the various centers have so far worked on solving these challenges mostly in isolation, and often disconnected from the accumulating body of relevant social science research. To provide an opportunity to exchange knowledge and to identify targets for better coordination among centers, NESCent, with funding from the NSF, co-organized and held a 2.5-day workshop that brought together informatics personnel from seven synthesis centers (NESCent, NCEAS, BioSynC, NIMBioS, ACEAS, SeSynC, iPlant), leaders of successful academic and private-sector cyberinfrastructure projects

(Galaxy, ITK, Google Refine), social scientists investigating the socio-technical aspects of developing sustainable and widely adopted cyberinfrastructure for scientific collaboration, and domain scientists with integrative research agendas in the evolutionary, ecological, and biodiversity sciences. The workshop resulted in a number of tangible as well as intangible outcomes. These include establishing venues for coordinating, discussing, and documenting collaborative science support technologies across centers, as well as identifying the features of successful cyberinfrastructure projects and the critical roles synthesis centers can play to foster and promote these projects.

Dendrobates leucomelas, a poisonous frog from Venezuelan Guiana, has higher aerobic capacity than its nontoxic relatives. PHOTO COURTESY OF CESAR BARRIO-AMOROS (WWW.ANDIGENA.ORG)

Evolutionary Tools in GMOD Hackathon and Chado Natural Diversity Module

NESCent sponsored and held a hackathon in late 2010 aimed at addressing critical gaps in the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) suite of tools that limit its utility for evolutionary research, specifically in the areas of viewing comparative genomics data, phylogenomic analysis and visualization, and supporting population-level genetic and phenotypic diversity data. Among many other significant results, the event provided an opportunity for several disparate development efforts to reconcile their requirements and data models for phenotype annotations and phenotype diversity experiments. Building on the

natural diversity schema developed years earlier at NESCent in collaboration with former sabbatical scholar W. Owen McMillan, the group, whose members came from fields as different as animal breeding, clade-based model databases, and morphological systematics, converged on a common schema extension to Chado, GMOD’s central relational schema. The extension, the Natural Diversity module, is now an official part of Chado, and has been submitted for publication to a special GMOD issue in the journal *Database*. Members of the hackathon group have since proceeded to develop visualizations and other tools on top of the module.

1. Center-wide Initiatives

This year, staff at the Center focused on the development of strategies for sustainability beyond 2014, when funding from the National Science Foundation ceases. These discussions have included our newly formed Oversight Committee, our Advisory Board, the major societies representing the evolutionary science community, and members of the academic community and senior administrators at our partner institutions.

2011 Activities

1.1.1 Oversight Committee

With the new round of funding, an Oversight Committee was constituted comprising senior academic administrators at Duke University, The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill and North Carolina State University, as well as the Chair and Vice-Chair of the Advisory Board. The Oversight Committee provides NSF with an evaluation of the performance of the NESCent directors, and also assists the Center's leaders in formulating strategy, particularly as this relates to the long-term goals and direction of the Center. The members of the Committee are:

- Dr. Chris Brown - (Assistant Vice Chancellor for Research Development, North Carolina State University)
- Dr. Robert Calderbank - (Dean of Natural Sciences, Duke University)
- Dr. Joseph Graves, Jr. - (Associate Dean for Research, Joint School of Nanotechnology and Nanoengineering, NCATSU & UNC-Greensboro, and Chair of the NESCent Advisory Board)
- Dr. Maria Orive - (Associate Professor, Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, Kansas University, and Vice-Chair of the NESCent Advisory Board)
- Dr. Jim Siedow - (Vice Provost for Research, Duke University)
- Dr. Carol Tresolini - (Associate Provost for Academic Initiatives, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill)

The Oversight Committee met with the NESCent directors, management team, operations committee and resident scientists on Feb 1 – 2, 2010. The Committee's report to the NSF on Mar 15, 2010, reflects their general approval of the Center's operations and its leaders.

One area of discussion that emerged in the context of NESCent's long-term future related to NESCent's engagement with its partner institutions. As noted by the Oversight Committee, a strong potential for continued Center support rests with these institutions. The Oversight Committee observed that NESCent's visibility at the partner institutions could be improved. In this regard, the Oversight Committee urged NESCent to explore ways to increase the relevance of the Center to faculty who may benefit from the Center's activities. The next section describes some of our efforts in this regard.

We are pleased that the Oversight Committee has become an important part of NESCent's advisory panel. Members of the Oversight Committee are senior administrators with full schedules, but they have unflinchingly made themselves available to the Center and its leaders.

Partner Institutions

Following recommendations to engage with our partner institutions, NESCent has instituted a Distinguished Speakers Seminar Series

at Duke University, the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, and North Carolina State University. The series includes a seminar and a reception hosted by NESCent. The first of these was held on Sep 7, 2010, and featured Mark Stoneking (Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology) at Duke University, Rick Ree (Field Museum of Natural History) at NCSU, and Maria Orive (Kansas University) at UNC-Chapel Hill. The goal is to have two sets of seminars a year, in the Spring and Fall semesters.

On a related note, the NSF Site Visit in May 2011 by Dr. Judy Verbeke (Acting Division Director, Biological Infrastructure) and Dr. Saran Twombly (NESCent's Cognizant Program Officer at the time), met with the Oversight Committee and the NESCent directors, and encouraged NESCent to consider developing pilot sponsored programs that involve PIs from the partner institutions, with a view to sustained engagement beyond 2014. As a consequence, NESCent has been working actively on the following projects:

- With Steve Walsh (Director of the Galapagos Research Center, UNC-Chapel Hill) to develop a NESCent Ambassador outreach program to educate guides and local scientists on evolutionary science
- With Brian Langerhans (Biology Department, NCSU), to develop an Ambassador program in Barbados.
- With Phil Morgan (Director of the Social Science Research Institute, Duke University) and Jim Moody (Director of the Duke Network Analysis Center, Duke University) to develop a catalysis meeting on the evolution of social networks, as part of our targeted activity focusing on evolution and the social sciences.
- With primatologists, evolutionary anthropologists, and the Duke Lemur Center, to explore the potential for collaborations between mathematicians, information scientists, and biologists in behavioral and life-history analyses.

1.1.3 Sustainability

Our efforts towards sustainability continue to focus on two related activities:

- Fact-finding and communication with stakeholders
- Development of a business plan

We discuss each of these in turn.

Fact-finding and communication with stakeholders

In addition to meeting with the Oversight Committee, NESCent's director Allen Rodrigo has met with senior members at Duke University including Provost Peter Lange of Duke University, and Dean Al Crumbliss, of Arts and Sciences, to discuss opportunities to secure financial support after 2014. As a consequence of these discussions, NESCent has started working with Duke University's Office of Corporate and Foundation Relations.

At the Evolution 2011 meeting in Norman, Oklahoma, Rodrigo also briefed the Joint Councils of the Society for the Study of Evolution, the Society for Systematic Biology and the American Society of Naturalists on NESCent's efforts for sustainability. We were also told of the results of the survey conducted by the Joint Councils on the future of evolution research. We are pleased that a majority of respondents (60%) believed unequivocally that there is value in continuing to fund an evolutionary synthesis center (only 9% responded with an unequivocal "No"). This is even more pleasing when we consider

the demographics of the respondents: 40% were students or postdoctoral scholars. Additionally, whereas most respondents (84%) unsurprisingly ranked individual grant support as the highest funding priority, more than 74% of respondents believed that the NSF should allocate 30% or more of its resources to large program awards including centers and networks.

Development of a business plan

At the September meeting of the Advisory Board, we devoted time to developing the outline of NESCent's business plan. This was done in three parts. First, since any discussion of sustainability requires that we understand what we are trying to sustain, we sought to identify NESCent's core values and commitments. The aim here was to identify the essence of NESCent as an organization — i.e., its “bottom-line.” Second, we laid out our value proposition. In particular, we sought to systematically identify the products, services, and resources that NESCent provides or can provide. Finally, we attempted to identify future stakeholders and funders who are likely to attach value to these outputs.

A draft of the business plan will be developed in time for the next Oversight Committee meeting next spring. This will serve as a platform for our fund-raising efforts in 2012 and beyond. In parallel with our business plan, NESCent is also developing a prospectus to assist with our fund-raising efforts.

1.1.4 New Initiatives at the Center

This year, many of the new initiatives that were in development in 2010 have come to fruition. In the following sections of this report, we describe these in greater detail. These include:

- The NESCent Academy
- The Journalist-in-residence program
- The Ambassador program
- The Darwin Day Roadshow
- The Evolution Video Competition
- The Cross-Center Postdoc Symposium
- The Cross-Center Cyberinfrastructure Meeting

In 2010, NESCent initiated two themed activities on evolutionary medicine, and astrobiology and synthetic biology. As part of these activities, in 2011, we sponsored two working groups focusing on the development of the curriculum for pre-medical and medical students, integrating evolutionary principles. We are also hosting a NESCent catalysis meeting on Astrobiology, Synthetic Biology, and Evolution from Oct 11 – 13, 2011. In addition to these, NESCent has also launched two new themed activities in 2011:

- Evolution education for K-12 underrepresented minorities
- Evolution and the social sciences

The first deadline for proposals was Sep 1, 2011, and there will be a second deadline in Jan 1, 2012.

NESCent is also submitting a proposal to host Evolution 2014, the annual joint meeting of the Societies for the Study of Evolution, Systematic Biology, and the American Society of Naturalists. Since 2014 is NESCent's last year of new funding, hosting this important meeting is a fitting way to thank the evolutionary science community for their support, and also to celebrate the science that NESCent has been a part of.

Finally, at the end of 2011, we expect to roll out our new website, which we believe will capture the vibrancy of NESCent's programs.

1.2 2012 Plans

NESCent will continue its focus on sustainability through 2012, and work with Duke University's Office of Corporate and Foundation Relations to identify potential sources of support. We will also continue to keep our stakeholders informed of NESCent's progress as it seeks to secure long-term funding.

Many of our new initiatives have been launched or piloted, e.g., the NESCent Academy, the Darwin Day Roadshow, and the Ambassador Program, and there may be opportunities to support these programs independently with awards from the NSF and other funding agencies, perhaps in collaboration with other institutions, organizations or centers.

pending, having just been submitted. The complete list of NESCent scientific projects funded in year 7 is given in the Appendices.

In the aggregate as of September 1st, NESCent supported 25 scientific meetings in year 7 (21 Working Group meetings and 4 Catalysis meetings), involving 396 visitors. In addition we hosted 6 meetings and 105 visitors by a variety of groups involved in evolutionary synthesis not supported by NESCent funds. A complete list of meetings at NESCent in year 7 is given in Appendix F.

2.1.1 The NESCent In-house Community and Postdoctoral Development

We have maintained a vibrant and collegial community of in-house scientists. During year 7, the Center will have hosted 18 postdoctoral fellows, 7 sabbatical scholars, 2 Triangle research fellows, 10 short-term visitors, 8 graduate students, and several visiting and resident scientists. We have also continually worked to improve the mentoring

and professional development program for our postdoctoral fellows. Each entering postdoctoral fellow meets with a mentoring committee to discuss the postdoctoral fellow's research plans, NESCent expectations, local and other resources; and the development of a written mentoring plan for each postdoctoral fellow.

In addition, we run a postdoctoral professional development program that, this year, included:

- A three-day NESCent Postdoctoral Retreat. This is the second year we have run this retreat. It included two half-day workshop on “Effective College Teaching,” targeted sessions on “The Publishing Process,” “Initiating and Maintaining Collaborations,” “Alternative Careers to Academia,” “Balancing Your Personal Life and Career at a Research 1 University,” “Dealing with Co-Authorship Issues,” and “Surviving Your First Year as a Faculty Member,” as well as multiple structured sessions to discuss research.
- A Postdoctoral Professional Development Seminar Series throughout the year, including recent sessions on “Mentoring Undergraduates”, “The Journal Process: From Submission to Print”, “Data Management Plans”, “Alternate Careers in Science”, and “The Faculty Search/Hiring Process”.

- On April 17th-20th 2011, NESCent hosted the first annual Joint Synthesis Center Postdoctoral Symposium for postdoctoral fellows from many of the synthesis centers. The symposium lasted three days and included a combination of brief research presentations by the postdocs, professional development activities, and breakout sessions on topics chosen by the fellows. A total of 31 postdoctoral fellows from 9 synthesis centers (ACEAS, BEACON, BioSynC, CEES, iPlant, NCEAS, NEON, NESCent, NIMBioS) attended. Topics of the major sessions included media training from AAAS, NSF Grant Writing, and Defining Synthesis. Breakout sessions dealt with a variety of topics including research, e.g. “New methods in biogeography”, outreach, e.g. “Thinking about broader impacts”, and professional development, e.g. “Time management”. Our detailed assessment indicates the first postdoctoral symposium was a success. Postdoctoral fellows were attracted from a broad assortment of centers and disciplinary backgrounds. The overlaps in research that occurred were balanced by multiple unique perspectives and therefore led to meaningful interactions among the attendees. In several cases these interactions have already led to collaborations. The fellows also deemed the informal discussions, planned development sessions, and break-out sessions to be of interest and beneficial. A combination of these also led to significant and positive attitude shifts in the fellows in terms of synthesis, outreach, and data.

2.1.2 New Initiatives in 2011

To jumpstart new areas of evolutionary synthesis we introduced two targeted initiatives in 2010: Evolutionary Medicine and Astrobiology, and the Origins of Life and Synthetic Biology. To further these initiatives we have conducted several activities in 2011:

- Feb., 2011 – NESCent's Communicating Human Evolution working group organized a symposium on human evolution at the AAAS annual meeting in Washington, DC, and a workshop for journalists on communicating human evolution at the Smithsonian Institution.

- April 2011 – NESCent put out a call for proposals to support a Working Group focusing on the development and implementation of model curricula and curriculum materials in Evolutionary Medicine to support teaching of undergraduates, and students in medicine, nursing, public health and medical research. We received five proposals and supported two: “Infusing Medical Education with Evolutionary Thinking” and “The Perils of Being Bipedal: an Evolutionary Perspective on Human Musculoskeletal Disorders”

- Summer, 2011 – Building on the Oct., 2010 EvoMed “mini-camp,” NESCent co-sponsored a two week, Continuing Medical Education workshop on evolutionary biology for medical practitioners and clinicians, held on Mt. Desert Island, ME.

- June 3-5, 2011 - With the University of California, San Francisco Center for Evolution and Cancer, NESCent sponsored a three-day symposium convening over 40 researchers in areas ranging from social science, genomics, epidemiology, and cellular processes on Evolution and Cancer.

- Dr. Lynn Rothschild, of the NASA Ames Research Center, is collaborating with us on the Astrobiology, the Origins of Life and Synthetic Biology initiative. A catalysis meeting is planned for October 2011 that includes 40 participants including international participants from Japan, United Kingdom, and Switzerland.

We have identified two new targeted initiatives and have advertised calls for proposals for both “Evolution and the Social Sciences” and “K-12 Evolution Education for Underrepresented Minorities.”

We have also initiated an intensive focus on understanding the processes that ensure that Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings are successful in terms of imitation stimulating collaboration and producing synthesis. As a first step, we sent Craig McClain, Assistant Director of Science, to become a certified meeting facilitator. The value of this is two-fold. One is to provide on-site facilitation services to group PIs who request it. The second is to utilize this knowledge to develop a best practices document and provide organizational and management training to group leaders to produce intended outcomes.

2.2 2012 Plans

In year 8, we will bring to fruition the second round of targeted initiatives, “Evolutionary Social Science” and “K-12 Evolution Education for Underrepresented Minorities.” We also anticipate a lively continuation of Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings in year 8. Thirteen groups are continuing from previous years, and we project another 7 groups will start in year 8, based on our most recent round of award decisions. Our in-house community of scientists will be at its largest ever, with 4-5 sabbatical scholars, 15 postdocs, and an exciting mix of short-term visitors and graduate student fellows.

2. Science and Synthesis

NESCent science includes a broad portfolio of scientific activities spanning a wide range of organisms, habitats, methods, and disciplines. Through support of postdoctoral fellows, long-term and short-term visiting scholars, and teams of scientists we have supported the use of synthetic methods to tackle many important evolutionary problems in year 7. Our in-house community continues to serve as a fertile environment for sustained research and allows diverse scientists to identify common interests and stimulate new collaborations.

2.1 2011 Activities

In year 7, NESCent's Calls for Proposals attracted 73 proposals for Working Groups, Catalysis Meetings, Sabbaticals, Postdoctoral Fellowships, or Courses. Of these, 29 were supported (see Appendices for summary).

We also attracted 17 applications for Short-term Visits and Graduate Fellowships in year 7. Of these 17, 8 have been supported and 8 are

3. Informatics

NESCent's Informatics activities continue to be driven by serving the informatics needs of visiting and resident scientists, and by removing common informatics-related barriers to synthetic research. Our activities combine software development, community coordination, institutional leadership, and human capacity building. In keeping with our goals, our accomplishments in the past year focused on (1) updating the suite of informatics tools and services we provide to the Center's scientists, in a way that harnesses cross-center opportunities for knowledge sharing; (2) providing leadership to the community on sharing, reusability, and interoperability of data; and (3) stepping up human capacity building in tackling informatics challenges commonly encountered by evolutionary scientists. Our Year 8 focus for Informatics will follow in the footsteps of previous years, with a particular emphasis on the reusability and future sustainability of the Center's software and data products.

3.1 2011 Activities

3.1.1 Informatics infrastructure for collaborative science

NESCent held a 2.5-day workshop on "Cyberinfrastructure for Collaborative Science," described in more detail under Highlights above. Based on the results of this workshop, we undertook a review of NESCent's suite of informatics technologies and services provided to sponsored scientists, and identified several needs currently underserved, or ripe for consolidating existing custom and external tools to a best-of-breed solution that is also reusable across scientific projects facing similar tasks. These areas include developing best-practice recommendations and supporting technologies for (1) efficient, scalable, and user-friendly file sharing; (2) collaboratively creating and maintaining reference collections; and (3) collaborative curation of comparative data matrices from the published literature. Technology evaluations are currently underway for all three, and the results will be implemented in the coming year as well as coordinated and shared with other synthesis centers.

3.1.2 Informatics products in support of sponsored scientists

In support of a working group we developed the Mammalian Feeding End-user Database (FEED), (see Highlights above). In another major informatics support project, we developed a tool for merging multiple authoritative taxonomy sources into a combined ontology with comprehensive annotations of synonyms in a joint collaboration with the working group on "Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology" and the Phenoscape project (<http://phenoscape.org>). The working group aims to compile from the literature a comprehensive data set on variation in visual system traits within the extant vertebrates. Using the tool, we created a combined vertebrate taxonomy ontology based on the Catalogue of Life (<http://catalogueoflife.org>) backbone for the purpose of reconciling taxon names cited in the literature that had meanwhile undergone various revisions.

3.1.3 Promoting the sharing, reusability, and interoperability of data

NESCent continues to take a leadership role in removing barriers to online access, reuse, and interpretation of data, both through externally funded initiatives as well as through Center-originated

initiatives aimed at promoting emerging standards and enhancing community resources. The Dryad Digital Data Repository (<http://datadryad.org>), funded by NSF for its startup phase, went through a series of quarterly releases that introduced numerous improvements, notably bi-directional hand-shaking with TreeBASE for phylogenetic data, and supporting privileged pre-publication access to deposited data for manuscript reviewers. Dryad's adoption has been steadily increasing, as evidenced by the rate of new depositions as well as by the diversity of journals in which the corresponding articles were published. People external to the project have started to exercise Dryad's programming interface (API), including creating an R package for data access. The Joint Data Archiving Policy (JDAP) was put in effect in January 2011 by seven leading journals in evolutionary biology. Through the Dryad-UK collaboration, funded by the UK Joint Information Science Committee (JISC), there is now a UK mirror of the Dryad repository at the British Library (BL), which reduces latency for European users of Dryad, and expands Dryad's disciplinary as well as geographic reach. A newly submitted NSF grant application would, if funded, support scaling up the repository to handle depositions at a rate at least an order of magnitude higher than present, and transitioning it to a self-sustaining and independently governed entity.

NESCent collaborates at several levels with the Data Observation Network for Earth (DataONE), an NSF OCI-funded virtual network of data repositories and registries in environmental science, ecology, and evolution. Dryad, one of the designated three initial member repositories, now natively supports the DataONE API required for member nodes. NESCent Informatics staff participate in DataONE's Core Cyberinfrastructure Team (CCIT), which defines and executes the network's cyberinfrastructure development plan, and in several DataONE working groups. This includes in particular the Data Integration and Semantics working group, which commenced in 2011 and is charged with guiding the CCIT in semantic data discovery and integration requirements and technologies.

The Phenoscape project (<http://phenoscape.org>), aiming to make the semantics of natural language descriptions of evolutionary phenotypes fully computable using ontologies, completely revamped the user-interfaces for its knowledgebase to implement the results from several rounds of usability testing. A public release of a 2.0 version, which will include a novel faceted browsing interface, is planned for the fall of 2011. The original NSF grant supporting the project expired in June 2011, but a new NSF ABI grant proposal submitted in 2010 was awarded and commenced in July 2011. It will fund a 4-year project on scaling up the ontological data annotation, reasoning, and semantic similarity methods to the level necessary for expanding the scope from teleost fishes to all vertebrates. The NSF-funded Phenotype Ontology Research Coordination Network (RCN), led by Paula Mabee, Andy Deans, Eva Huala, and Suzi Lewis had its first large meeting at NESCent, and a second more focused one at Google in Boulder, CO. The latter provided an opportunity to preview Google's developing platform for custom collaborative editing applications, such as for ontologies.

NESCent Informatics staff Hilmar Lapp co-organized two workshops at the 2010 Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) Conference. One of these, a 1-day hands-on working meeting of the Phylogenetic Standards Interest Group (<http://www.tdwg.org/activities/phylogenetics/>), gave rise to an in-depth technical report on Best Practices for Publishing Trees, which is currently being turned into a manuscript. The working meeting and report also spurred renewed

interest in the Minimum Information for a Phylogenetic Analysis (MIAPA) reporting standard and related research into use-cases for and barriers to reuse of phylogenetic analysis results. At the TDWG Conference in fall 2011, a follow-up workshop, co-organized by Lapp, will take place with the goal to converge on requirements for a MIAPA standard from the perspective of biodiversity science applications.

The Board of Directors of the Phyloinformatics Research Foundation, a recently established not-for-profit to provide governance and strategic oversight to the community resources Tree of Life Web Project (<http://tolweb.org>) and TreeBASE (<http://treebase.org>), had its first meeting in December 2010 at NESCent. Its next meeting will also take place at NESCent, in late fall 2011. The Board includes NESCent Informatics staff Karen Cranston. Lapp is PI on a collaborative NSF ABI proposal submission that aims to make archival and synthesis of published phylogenetic knowledge significantly more scalable and rewarding to authors, and that would for the first time make TreeBASE and TolWeb interoperable.

3.1.4 Promoting open-source development of reusable and standards-supporting tools

NESCent sponsored a hackathon on improving the GMOD suite of tools to improve its utility for evolutionary research, described in more detail below. Recently departed postdoctoral fellow Liam Revell has made available the open-source R package phytools, which includes comparative phylogenetic methods he developed while at NESCent. The package is now available in CRAN, the central package repository for the R language. Revell is also a prolific contributor to answering queries surrounding the application of comparative phylogenetic methods on the community mailing list R-SIG-Phylo, which is one of the outcomes of the Comparative Methods in R hackathon held by NESCent in December 2007.

The Center has established an organization umbrella account on the Github source code repository (<http://github.com/nescent>). One of the strengths of Github is in promoting micro-contributions by external developers, due to the distributed nature of git, the underlying version control system, and a number of features that support the social aspect of collaborative software development. We have committed to start all future software projects in support of sponsored science on Github, and existing ones are being consolidated under the umbrella account.

After NESCent helped kick off the highly successful inaugural Conference on Informatics for Phylogenetics, Evolution, and Biodiversity (iEvoBio) in 2010, the Center also sponsored and co-organized (H. Lapp) the second iEvoBio conference in 2011, with the same goal of promoting collaborative, open-source software and standards development in the fields of evolution and biodiversity. The meeting took place again in conjunction with the annual Evolution Meetings, in Norman, Oklahoma. It had over 110 registrants. In addition to the program elements present in 2010, the 2011 conference featured a special session on Metagenomics, Barcoding, and Biodiversity. The session was co-sponsored by the NSF-funded RCN for the Genomics Standards Consortium (RCN4GSC) as part of its charge to bridge between biodiversity information standards, such as Darwin Core, and genomics standards, such as the MIxS family of minimum reporting checklists for metagenomics sequencing experiments. The conference was received with similarly enthusiastic feedback as in the first year, despite higher registration costs and significantly fewer registrants.

3.1.5 Informatics Training Internships

The NESCent-cosponsored Computational Phyloinformatics course (held annually since 2007; see Section 4.1.5) was held this year in Japan, with a module on using the emerging PhyloWS standard for programmatic access to online data resources added to the curriculum. PhyloWS is a product of the Evolutionary Informatics working group, and of the EvoIO interoperability initiative (<http://evoio.org>) that formed from it. The Center also hosted a half-day tutorial on using Google Refine, a powerful tool for cleaning up tabular data culled from heterogeneous sources.

For the 5th year in a row, NESCent served as a mentoring organization in the Google Summer of Code. With financial support from Google, eight students worked remotely with mentors over the summer on open-source, collaborative software development projects (for details of each project see http://informatics.nescent.org/wiki/Phyloinformatics_Summer_of_Code_2011).

Additional internships in information science and informatics were sponsored through the NSF INTEROP Virtual Data Center project. NESCent-DataONE postdoctoral fellow Heather Piwowar and NESCent Informatics staff Lapp mentored graduate student summer interns on a project tracking the reuse of data sets deposited in select data repositories, including TreeBASE, and on integrating data held by DataONE member repositories (such as Dryad) into the global web of Linked Data, respectively (see <https://notebooks.dataone.org/> for open project notebooks for both projects).

3.2 2012 Plans

In the coming year, we plan to focus special attention on four areas:

(1) The Center's resident scholars, in particular postdocs, often have very specific informatics training needs that arise from their project-related research tasks, and that are not well served by the informatics courses already run within the NESCent Academy course program. We will run short, focused hands-on training activities designed specifically for NESCent resident scholars to teach informatics skills useful for furthering their research projects. Commonly requested subjects include database design, and scripting comparative analyses in R.

(2) The experiences shared across centers at the Cyberinfrastructure for Collaborative Science workshop (see above) confirmed that usability and user-experience are major factors in determining the effectiveness of informatics tools developed for or deployed to scientists. To improve the effectiveness and adoption of our informatics products, we will subject the user-interfaces of products under active development to usability and user-experience evaluation and improvement studies. This will happen across the board, including externally funded products from our cyberinfrastructure initiatives such as Dryad and Phenoscape.

(3) Finding and accessing relevant data online, and integrating such data so that they are useful to one's research questions remains a significant challenge to data sharing and reuse. We will continue to play a leadership role for the evolutionary science community in promoting standards and infrastructure for online discovery, access, and reuse of interoperable data. Specifically, we will advance and demonstrate best practices by improving the discoverability, interoperability, documentation, and reuse-oriented packaging of data compiled under NESCent sponsorship.

(4) NESCent has created numerous online informatics products over its lifetime in support of the work its scientists, and will create more until NSF support for the Center expires in 2014. These resources are highly heterogeneous in purpose and function that they provide, ranging from tools that allow groups to collaborate more effectively, to online databases referenced in journal publications, to software

source code. The needs and use-cases for keeping these resources available beyond the lifetime of the Center differ widely, as do the opportunities for and vested interests in sustaining them for the long term. We will develop a comprehensive strategy for how the Informatics products of the Center can best be sustained, or kept available, beyond the expiration of NSF support for the Center.

4. Education and Outreach

NESCent's 2011 Education and Outreach activities reflect a successful blending of established programs with several new initiatives. Both the new and existing activities fit within the framework of what have become the five pillars of NESCent Education/Outreach:

- Outreach to the Education Community
- Outreach to the General Public
- Outreach to Underrepresented Minorities
- Outreach to International Science and Education Communities
- “Inreach” to the Science Community

4.1 2011 Activities

4.1.1 Outreach to the Education Community

In partnership with AIBS, our annual Evolution Symposium was organized as part of the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT) annual conference. Entitled “Molecular Insights in Classic Examples of Evolution” it featured four internationally known researchers, and was once again accessible via live webcast. We developed, produced and distributed a CD ROM of learning resources and offered a half day, hands on teacher workshop to complement the symposium.

Other activities included:

- Our annual three day summer workshop for high school instructors (this year it was held in Madison, WI), as well as multiple other workshops, short talks and presentations for high school teachers on effective strategies for teaching evolution.
- Our successful “Evolution in the News” feature and podcast series, in partnership with the Understanding Evolution website.
- The first annual “NESCent Evolution Video Contest” held at the Evolution Societies meeting in Norman, OK. (See “Highlights” for more information.)
- The Communicating Human Evolution working group led by Norman Johnson, continued its efforts focusing on activities related to science education and pedagogy, science journalism and citizen science. Some of the successful activities from this working group over the past year include:
- Organization and delivery of a symposium on Human Evolution at the 2011 AAAS meeting in Washington, DC, and a related workshop for journalists on communicating human evolution, held the evening prior at the Smithsonian;

- Organization and delivery of a one day Evolutionary Medicine “Mini Camp” for medical practitioners, followed by co-sponsorship a two week summer course for CME credit on evolutionary medicine at the Mount Desert Island Biological Laboratory in Maine;
- Acceptance of a manuscript (“Why Are Chimps Still Chimps?”) to appear in the Feb. 2012 issue of American Biology Teacher (special issue on human evolution);
- Preparation and submission of an NSF TUES grant to fund development of a Human Evolution instructional website

4.1.2 Outreach to the General Public

The highlight of our outreach efforts for the general public continued to be the annual Darwin Day event we cofounded and co-sponsor with the North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences. This day-long event attracted several thousand visitors to the museum on Feb. 12th, 2011. NESCent hosted the keynote speaker (Dr. Lynn Rothschild of NASA-AMES), ran several interactive stations and booths and organized an undergraduate/graduate research poster contest as part of the event.

NESCent also sponsored or co-sponsored several other evolution-related talks for the general public, many in partnership with the NC Museum of Natural Sciences. One of the highlights was a public lecture on April 11th by Rosemary and Peter Grant. In partnership with the museum and NC State Universities Keck Center for Behavioral Biology, NESCent sponsored their talk and a reception in their honor.

By far, one of our biggest and most exciting outreach events for the general public was the 2011 NESCent Darwin Day Roadshow (see below for more information).

4.1.3 Outreach to Underrepresented Minorities

We continued to organize and run a collection of evolution outreach activities at the annual SACNAS (Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science) conference.

We once again collaborated with Scott Edwards (Harvard) and Rich Kliman (Cedar Crest College) on the Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution program, which sends 25 undergraduates to the annual Evolution (SSE/SSB/ASN) conference and provides them with mentoring and professional development while there.

One of our new minority outreach initiatives in 2011 is the after-school science project, “Seeing and Learning Science After School” (SALSA).

We continued the NESCent MSI Faculty Travel Award program, which this year sent four faculty members from minority serving institutions to the Evolution 2011 Conference in Norman, OK to present original research, and mentor diverse undergraduates.

Travel awards (maximum of \$500) were given to 22 students from underrepresented minority groups to participate in short courses and workshops offered by the NESCent Academy (see “Inreach” section).

We issued a request for proposals for evolution education programs focused on underrepresented minorities at the K-12 level and will be reviewing proposals and issuing awards in the very near future. We anticipate several innovative minority outreach projects will result from this initiative.

Dr. Weigang Qiu (Hunter College) spent much of 2011 in residence at NESCent as part of our Targeted MSI Sabbatical program. A significant amount of his efforts were spent on evolution curriculum development projects that will directly benefit his students at Hunter, consistently ranked as one of the most diverse urban undergraduate campuses in the United States.

Finally, we received a grant from the European Society of Evolutionary Biology to translate our Evolution in the News stories and podcasts into Spanish, to dramatically increase the audience for these resources, and enhance their impact on underrepresented minority student populations. The translation and dissemination of these resources will occur throughout the coming year.

4.1.4 Outreach to International Science and Education Communities

NESCent dramatically increased our international outreach efforts in the past year via the NESCent Ambassador program (ambassadors. nescent.org), which sends NESCent scientists and educators to deliver short workshops and consulting in evolutionary science, informatics and education in developing nations. In April of this year, we received \$264,515 in the form of an NSF EAGER grant to pilot this program for two years.

To date, we have already sent eight scientists to Ecuador/Galapagos, Indonesia and Madagascar. In the coming months, several more NESCent scientists and educators will be visiting multiple Caribbean

nations, and Kenya, with return trips planned to the Galapagos and Bali, Indonesia. Each ambassadorship involves at least one NESCent postdoc, in addition to senior NESCent scientists/education staff. These ambassadorships not only increase our international presence and provide valuable scientific training and expertise around the world, but also serve as unique professional development opportunities for NESCent scientists.

4.1.5 “Inreach” to the Science Community

NESCent made great strides to expand and formalize our “inreach” efforts to the evolutionary science and informatics communities by collecting all of the short courses and workshops we offer under the umbrella of the newly established NESCent Academy (academy. nescent.org), and hiring Dr. Karen Cranston to oversee this effort in her role as Training Coordinator and Bioinformatics Project Manager.

This year, the NESCent Academy sponsored two new courses:

- Evolutionary Quantitative Genetics – Principle Instructors: Stevan Arnold and Joe Felsenstein, plus four guest instructors; 25 students; 10 from under-represented minorities, one international student.
- Next-generation Sequencing: Data Acquisition, Comparative Genomics, Design and Analysis for Population Genetics, Systematics and Development – Principle Instructors: Brian O’Connor and Alexie Papanicolaou, plus seven guest instructors; nearly 30 students from diverse career stages, graduate student to faculty.

NESCent Academy also co-sponsored four courses:

- Practical Computing for Biologists at North Carolina State University
- Computational Phyloinformatics in Kyoto, Japan
- Evolution and Medicine at Mount Desert Island Biological Laboratory
- AnthroTree Workshop at University of Massachusetts, Amherst

We continued to organize and conduct a weekly seminar series for in house scientists and invited speakers from the local (NC Triangle) area. We also continued the “NESCent Director’s Seminar Series” to bring in more diverse speakers from outside the Triangle area to NESCent.

4.2 2012 Plans

In the coming year, we will continue to offer the collection of activities and education/outreach resources upon which our solid foundation is built. We anticipate that our relatively new programs, such as the Darwin Day Roadshow and Evolution Film Festival will receive even more interest and attention than they did during their first years. Our NESCent Ambassador program will continue to expand, with ambassadorships to two new locations (the Caribbean and Kenya). We are piloting a new program that will send our scientists to after-school programs and community centers serving underrepresented minority students to lead hands-on activities exploring evolutionary science. We anticipate the initiation of several projects growing out of our targeted initiative on K-12 evolution education for underrepresented minorities and the completion of project designed to translate Evolution in the News stories/podcasts into Spanish. In summary, we will continue to do what we do well, and aggressively explore new partnerships and new ways to build on the five pillars of NESCent Education and Outreach.

5. Science Communications

In keeping with NSF's Broader Impact goal of disseminating results, NESCent's communications office acts as a liaison between the Center and its many outside audiences. Activities include writing news releases, managing our online presence through our website and social media, producing a quarterly newsletter, assisting scientists in responding to media requests, and providing media training and other communication-related workshops for scientists at NESCent as well as partner institutions.

5.1 2011 Activities

5.1.1 NESCent in the news

We continue to produce a regular stream of news in evolutionary science for use by the media. In 2011 we wrote and distributed more than a dozen news releases highlighting major results from NESCent-sponsored projects. Reporters receive these releases through an online news service sponsored by the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS). You can also follow these stories on our website at nescent.org/news/News_releases.php.

In the past year these news releases received more than 32,000 page views by registered reporters and journalists, according to traffic statistics provided by AAAS. This resulted in more than 65 news articles in the mainstream media, including Science Magazine, NPR, Scientific American, Discovery Channel, Wired, The New York Times, and TIME Magazine. Collectively these outlets reach millions of readers each month. Some of the most successful news stories of the past year include:

- "Primates are more resilient than other animals to environmental ups and downs" (December 1, 2010) What sets mankind's closest relatives — monkeys, apes, and other primates — apart from other animals? One answer is that primates are less susceptible to seasonal variability, particularly in rainfall, finds a new study. This story was picked up by TIME Magazine.
- "To age is primate" (March 10, 2011) The first-ever comparison of human aging patterns with those in chimps and other primates suggests the pace of human aging may not be so unique after all, despite our relatively long life spans and access to modern medicine. This story was picked up by more than 100 news outlets, including Discovery News, US News & World Report, ABC News, MSNBC, Science Magazine, USA Today, CBS News, and NPR's Science Friday.
- "Treadmill tests for poison frogs prove toxic species are more physically fit" (March 29, 2011) The most toxic, brightly colored members of the poison frog family may also be the best athletes, finds NESCent postdoc Juan Santos (see Highlights for more). This story was picked up by Wired Science, Discovery Channel, and MSNBC News.
- "Songbirds tweak their tunes in different ways to cope with clamor" (May 26, 2011) Some birds that live near noisy sites can alter their songs to deal with din. But closely related species with similar songs may tweak their tunes in different ways, says a study by NESCent postdoc Clint Francis. This story was picked up by US News and World Report and Science Magazine.

In addition to gaining news coverage for NESCent-sponsored science, we also organized several outreach events that received national media

attention, including our newly-launched evolution film festival, which was featured in two articles in the UK Guardian, and our first-ever Darwin Day Roadshow, which was featured in The New York Times.

For a full list of NESCent media coverage in 2011 please see Appendix H.

5.1.2 NESCent by the numbers

The audience for NESCent's other communication channels continues to grow. Readers can learn about research and training opportunities, new initiatives, and upcoming events by subscribing to our quarterly newsletter. You can also visit NESCent on Twitter, Facebook, and YouTube. In the past year, these and other channels saw the following increases in readership:

- News articles: > 65 articles in mainstream outlets (up from 40 for last year)
- Website: 77,000 visitors from 176 countries in the past year (up from 66,000 visitors from 54 countries last year)
- Newsletter: 3,200+ subscribers (up from 2,000 for last year)
- Twitter: 1,175 followers (up from 430 for last year)

5.2 2012 Plans

Looking ahead, one of our goals for the next year is to enhance our online presence. To that end we've been planning a new look for the NESCent website, which was last redesigned in 2006. The current site receives roughly 30,000 page views a month, from visitors looking for everything from classroom resources to upcoming proposal deadlines. With help from our longtime partners at the American Institute for Biological Sciences, the new design will allow us to feature our proposal deadlines and award winners more prominently on the home page. The new site will also better showcase some of NESCent's new initiatives — such as the NESCent Academy and the NESCent Ambassador Program — which did not exist at the time of the last site design. See a preview of the new design at <http://stage.nescent.org/>. The new site will be launched this fall.

Another one of our goals for the next year is to support continued news coverage of evolution beyond the Center. Our efforts come at a time when newspapers, magazines, and broadcast media have been laying off science journalists at an alarming rate. To support continued coverage of evolution and related fields, we have two programs:

- NESCent's journalist-in-residence program offers a unique opportunity for reporters, producers, and editors to work on an ambitious, exciting project of their own choosing with an evolutionary focus. Fellowships are open to salaried or freelance journalists in print, electronic or broadcast media. Journalists of all nationalities are welcome to apply. Proposals are considered twice a year, with deadlines on January 15 and July 10. Our first journalist in residence was public radio reporter Molly Samuel from NPR member station KQED in San Francisco. Samuel was on-site for two weeks in April 2011 to interview experts for a sixty-minute public radio documentary on island biogeography, conservation, and climate change. Read more about her project at californiasislands.com/about/.

We expect to host two additional journalists this fall:

- Freelance journalist Michael Martin proposes to write an article (which he hopes will form the beginnings of a book) about the unusual life and work of evolutionary biologist Margie Profet, whose controversial ideas about the evolution of asthma and menstruation earned her a MacArthur Foundation Genius grant in 1993, but who mysteriously went missing in 2005. Martin's project fits in nicely with NESCent's ongoing initiatives in evolutionary medicine. Martin has written articles for Science, The Scientist, Harvard Magazine, and United Press International. Martin will join us for the month of October.
- Award-winning essayist and journalist Ilan Greenberg intends to interview experts for a series of articles about emerging infectious

diseases with animal origins, such as West Nile virus and mad cow disease. His work has strong potential to help highlight the intersection of evolution with other fields, particularly biosecurity and global public health. Greenberg has written for The New York Times, National Geographic, Wall Street Journal, Slate, Harper's and GQ, among others. He will join us for two months starting in November.

NESCent also sponsors a blog contest and conference travel fellowship for evolutionary bloggers. To apply for the award, writers are required to submit a blog post that highlights current or emerging evolutionary research. Winners receive \$750 apiece to cover travel and lodging expenses to attend ScienceOnline, a science communication conference held each January in North Carolina. Previous winners include graduate students Danielle Lee, Neil Losin, Christie Wilcox and Jeremy Yoder.

Press Coverage of NESCent Science and Activities for Year 7

Postdoctoral fellows

JOSH AULD:

"Biological clock ticks slower for female birds who choose good mates" (*Eurekalert*)

"Biological clock ticks slower for female birds who choose good mates" (*Science 360*, National Science Foundation)

"Biological clock ticks slower for female birds who choose good mates" (*USA Today*)

"How male birds affect female fertility" (*MSNBC*)

CARLOS BOTERO:

"Climate for divorce" (*Science News*)

CLINTON FRANCIS:

"Songbirds tweak their tunes in different ways to cope with clamor" (*Eurekalert*)

"C'mon feel the noise: Related songbirds respond differently to noise pollution, possibly complicating conservation efforts" (*Science Magazine*)

"Songbirds tweak their tunes in different ways to cope with clamor" (*Science 360* news highlights from NSF)

"Songbirds adapt to noisy environments" (*US News and World Report*)

"When birds go to town" (*Science News*)

JENNY MCGUIRE:

"Climate changes, and there goes the neighborhood" (*ScienceNews*)

"Study offers warning about next potential mass extinction" (*USA Today*)

"Earth's sixth mass extinction: is it almost here?" (*National Science Foundation*)

RAFAEL RUBIO DE CASAS:

"The future of a fog oasis" (*Scientific American*)

JUAN SANTOS:

"Treadmill tests for poison frogs prove toxic species are more physically fit" (*Eurekalert*)

"Poisonous lifestyle makes frogs more fit" (*Wired Science*)

"Treadmill test reveals most poisonous frogs are best frog athletes" (*Discovery Channel: Animal Planet*)

"Athletic frogs: Go bold or go home" (*Futurity*)

"Froggy fitness: toxic species prove most athletic" (*LiveScience*)

"Poison frog athletes" (*California Academy of Sciences*)

"Poison dart frogs leap to the top for frog fitness" (*MSNBC News*)

STEPHEN SMITH:

"Single parenthood doesn't pay off for plants" (*Eurekalert*)

PETER UNMACK:

"Little Aussie Batter" (*Good Weekend Magazine*, Melbourne)

GREGOR YANEGA:

"Hummingbirds catch flying bugs with the help of fast-closing beaks" (*Eurekalert*)

Press Coverage of NESCent Science and Activities for Year 7

Catalysis meetings and working groups

LAUREN BUCKLEY ET AL.: MECHANISTIC DISTRIBUTION MODELS: ENERGETICS, FITNESS, AND POPULATION DYNAMICS

“Coping with climate change” (*Eurekalert*)

ALEXEI DRUMMOND ET AL.: SOFTWARE FOR BAYESIAN EVOLUTIONARY ANALYSIS BY SAMPLING TREES:

“Ancestry of polar bears traced to Ireland” (*ScienceDaily*)

NORMAN JOHNSON ET AL.: COMMUNICATING THE RELEVANCE OF HUMAN EVOLUTION

“Panelists to discuss evolution of human brain size, skin color and diet at AAAS meeting” (*Eurekalert*)

“Thinking big” (*Science News*)

“Eating meat drove the evolution of our big, powerful brain” (*AAAS Meeting Coverage. National Association of Science Writers*)

“Human brain evolution and creatine gene expression” (*Scitable*)

“Just how big a deal is milk drinking?” (*Scientific American*)

KEN KOZAK ET AL.: MONTANE DIVERSITY IN SPACE AND TIME: LINKING EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY AND MACROECOLOGY

“Stable temperatures boost biodiversity in tropical mountains” (*Eurekalert*)

JONATHAN PAYNE ET AL.: PHANEROZOIC BODY SIZE TRENDS IN TIME AND SPACE: MACROEVOLUTION AND MACROECOLOGY

“Marine snails get a metabolism boost” (*Eurekalert*)

KAREN STRIER AND SUSAN ALBERTS: EVOLUTIONARY ECOLOGY OF PRIMATE LIFE HISTORIES

“Primates are more resilient than other animals to environmental ups and downs” (*Eurekalert*)

“Planet of the apes...and monkeys and humans” (*TIME Magazine*)

“Primates better adapted to environmental changes” (*Birmingham Star*)

“Primates best at coping with change” (*St. Louis Globe-Democrat*)

“Lovely weather for ducks and primates” (*Futurity*)

“Aging rates, gender gap in mortality similar across all primates” (*Eurekalert*)

“Humans age at same rate as chimps, gorillas” (*Discovery News*)

“Humans age at same pace as other primates, study finds” (*US News & World Report*)

“Humans, apes, have similar aging patterns” (*ABC News*)

“What do you mean I’m aging like a baboon?!” (*MSNBC News*)

“Study finds primates age gracefully” (*National Science Foundation*)

“Science podcast” (*Science Magazine*)

“To age is primate” (*Duke News*)

“Humans, apes, have similar aging patterns” (*USA Today*)

“Nonhuman primates and humans have similar aging patterns, study shows” (*Los Angeles Times*)

“Despite long lives, humans age like other primates” (*NPR’s Science Friday*)

“Talk of the Nation: Despite long lives, humans age like other primates” (*NPR*)

“Humans, primates age in similar ways” (*CBS News*)

“Humans, apes, have similar aging patterns” (*Seattle Times*)

“Humans, monkeys age the same way” (*Futurity*)

“Time marches on for aging people in about the same way as for our primate cousins, study finds” (*News Radio Toronto*)

“When it comes to aging, we’re just like monkeys” (*The Globe and Mail*)

“Research insights: What it means to be human” (*The Examiner*)

Press Coverage of NESCent Science and Activities for Year 7

Visiting scholars

RYAN CALSBEEK

“Of lizards, female choice and male competition” (*Science in the Triangle*)

TAL PUPKO

“New study pinpoints why some microbial genes are more promiscuous than others” (*Eurekalert*)

Education and outreach group

DARWIN DAY ROAD SHOW

“A nationwide day for honoring Charles Darwin, but handled with caution” (*New York Times*)

“It’s cool, really, we promise” (*GenomeWeb*)

“Evolution: Only in America” (*BioJobBlog*)

NESCENT EVOLUTION FILM FESTIVAL

“Cold-blooded cannibals: extreme adaptations to island life” (*UK Guardian*)

“Crafty island plants use lizards to disperse their seeds” (*UK Guardian*)

NESCent leadership and staff

JOEL KINGSOLVER

“Evolution drives many plants and animals to be bigger, faster” (*Eurekalert*)

“The mass extinction of scientists who study species” (*Wired Magazine*)

“Scientists take Charles Darwin on the road” (*Miller-McCune*)

“Life under constant pressure” (*Miller-McCune*)

6. Assessment

NESCent’s assessment program seeks to evaluate whether we are fulfilling our mission and core values. NESCent’s mission is to “promote the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge to address significant, emerging, or novel questions in evolutionary science and its applications. NESCent achieves this by supporting research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries.” Specifically, we apply a three-tier evaluative system focused on people, products, and process. We seek to determine whether:

- People: NESCent supports research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries.
- Products: NESCent scientists are addressing questions that are significant, emerging, and/or novel in evolutionary science.
- Process: NESCent accomplishes (2) by promoting the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge both within and beyond direct Center activities.

6.1 Year 7 Activities

6.1.1 Ongoing Activities

NESCent’s assessment program continues to mature. In this last year we have developed a cohesive assessment program across our three divisions. This includes both developing an assessment strategy for

our current 5-year cycle and identifying specific data and analyses to meet our assessment objectives. Part of this maturation has been to develop and refine our three evaluative tiers. As a demonstration of the progress NESCent has made in our assessment program, in April of this year we produced our first assessment report to NSF providing 35 pages of detailed analyses that spanned our three tiers and all three divisions. Here, we highlight a few of these analyses to demonstrate the breadth of our program.

- Since the center’s inception the total number of visitors continues to grow with no signal of leveling or diminishing. Annually, ~54% of participants in NESCent activities are new to the center.
- Over years 1-7 of the center, participants have represented 50 countries from every inhabited continent.
- NESCent programs on average have 30% female representation both in terms of PIs and participants, which is higher than current NSF estimates of women with PhDs practicing in biology. Also, in all but one year, 2006, NESCent has offered a greater percentage of postdoctoral fellowships to females than represented in our applicant pool.
- NESCent publications covered approximately three times the subject categories than comparison groups. NESCent publications traverse a range of disciplines incorporating much more than just evolutionary biology.

- NESCent papers contain on average a greater number of authors and affiliations than comparison groups.
- As measured by number of authors, departments, departmental types, etc., NESCent Postdoctoral Fellows are more collaborative.
- Working groups that incorporate a greater percentage of minorities and emerging scientists are more productive

Since our assessment report we have also finished constructing a list of grants resulting from NESCent activities. Since 2007, scientists have obtained more than \$22,777,000 in additional grant support as a direct result of their involvement with NESCent supported programs, e.g. working groups, sabbaticals, postdoctoral fellows. This estimate does not include those grants, e.g. Dryad, Phenoscape, DataOne, GMOD, obtained by our informatics group that have generated considerable additional funds.

From our analyses this last year and described in the Assessment Report, we learned that when compared with most universities, regardless of how we define the comparison group, NESCent has a high citation per paper rate and a low percentage of uncited papers. We examined two sets of universities: 1) the top 40 universities in terms of R&D spending according to 2009 NSF data, and 2) a randomly-selected set of 120 colleges and universities. Funding data was retrieved from the WebCASPAR database. In terms of publications per \$100,000 of funding, NESCent ranked 7th-highest among Top-40 universities and 38th-highest among the randomly-selected schools with 2.12 publications per \$100,000. When number of citations per \$10,000 was analyzed, NESCent ranked 10th among Top-40 universities and 22nd among the randomly-selected schools with an average of 2.07 citations per \$10,000. NESCent also had a low percent-uncited rate of 7.78%, which places the center 7th-lowest among the Top 40 universities.

6.1.1.1 Tier 1 Assessment

Over the last year we have accomplished the transition of much of our Tier 1 assessment into an automated and replicable process. The majority of the data needed for assessment is collected with our internal NESCent Administrative Database (NEAD) that serves as the backbone for all the Center's evaluative activities. The strength of NEAD rests on data entry occurring from multiple users from center Directors and administrative staff to individual participants in NESCent activities. Virtually every aspect of NESCent's day-to-day operations, e.g. meeting registration, the proposal process, and updating the website, require utilizing the web-based interface in NEAD. This ensures that we accurately collect a wide range of data needed for assessment activities with an automated process. With an accurate database available, up-to-date and prompt assessment reports are available.

6.1.1.2 Tier 2 Assessment

For Tier 2 assessment in Year 7, we have focused on building accurate records of publications and grants resulting from NESCent activities. By establishing this record, we are now able to easily produce up-to-date estimates of the number of publications and citations. In Year 7 we have so far produced 40 papers compared to the 42 papers from last year at this time. NESCent's h-index rose from 26 to 32 and our papers have garnered an additional 1,116 citations for a cumulative total of 4,711 (an average of 16.13 citations per item). We continue to work with Chaomei Chen

(Drexel University), in developing a co-citation network of NESCent publications. This will allow us to examine the disciplinary diversity of these publications and the extent to which they bridge different scientific domains. We are also maintaining our collaboration with

Gender of Project PI's and Co-PI's from 12/1/10-8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	GRADUATE FELLOW	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Female	9	2	1	2	8	4	17	43
Male	19	8	4	3	12	5	31	82
Do not wish to provide	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
TOTAL	28	13	5	5	20	9	48	128

Ethnicity of Project PI's and Co-PI's from 12/1/10-8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	GRADUATE FELLOW	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Hispanic or Latino	2	0	0	1	3	0	3	9
Not Hispanic or Latino	24	10	5	4	17	9	40	109
Do not wish to provide	2	3	0	0	0	0	5	10
TOTAL	28	13	5	5	20	9	48	128

Race of Project PI's and Co-PI's from 12/1/10-8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	GRADUATE FELLOW	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Asian	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	5
Black/African American	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Do not wish to provide	2	5	0	0	1	0	6	14
Hispanic/Latino	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Native Hawaiian/ Other Pacific Islander	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
White	24	8	5	3	16	8	39	103
TOTAL	27	13	5	4	18	9	46	122

Countries of Participant Institutions

ARGENTINA	3	ISRAEL	1
AUSTRALIA	17	ITALY	1
AUSTRIA	2	JAPAN	3
BRAZIL	2	MEXICO	2
BULGARIA	1	NETHERLANDS	4
CANADA	29	NEW ZEALAND	4
CHINA	1	NORWAY	1
CROATIA	1	ROMANIA	1
DENMARK	1	SOUTH AFRICA	1
FINLAND	2	SPAIN	1
FRANCE	5	SWEDEN	4
GERMANY	17	SWITZERLAND	7
HUNGARY	1	UNITED KINGDOM	55
INDIA	2	UNITED STATES	541
IRELAND	1	GRAND TOTAL	711

PARTICIPANTS BY COUNTRY

Disciplines of Supported Projects in Year 7

VISITING SCHOLAR

CENTER PROJECT

COURSE

MEETING

Jason Priem (U. of North Carolina, Chapel Hill) on generating alt-metrics for NESCent publications. Briefly, alt-metrics are alternative measures to citations that quantify a paper's impact. Alt-metrics include such things as paper downloads, Twitter and Facebook links to a paper, and how many times the paper has been accessed or read in Zotero and Mendeley. Our preliminary analyses indicate that NESCent publications have occurred 685 times on blogs registered by Google, 246 times in CiteULike, 3,563 times in Mendeley, and 217 times in Regtranbase.

6.1.1.3 Tier 3 Assessment

For Tier 3 assessment in Year 7, we continue to work with Dr. Jonathon Cummings (Associate Professor of Management, Fuqua School of Business, Duke University) on the "Science of Science" project. This project examines how NESCent influences researcher engagement in synthetic evolutionary science through working groups, catalysis meetings, and informatics hackathons. For example, participants are surveyed during and after their visits to NESCent, with questions targeting the nature of interdisciplinary research, extent of collaboration, impact of NESCent participation, and generation of new knowledge. Chris Shields (Program Coordinator for the "Science of Science" project) was very effective in collecting survey data during his 2 years working at NESCent. He was able to collect surveys from 408 participants from 29 working groups, 246 participants from 9 catalysis meetings, and 57 participants from 2 informatics hackathons. Though the number of participants may appear large, the unit of analysis is the working group, catalysis meeting, or informatics hackathon, thus the sample size is still relatively small for statistical purposes (29, 9, and 2, respectively). Thus, by collecting survey data over time, there will be multiple observations from each unit, thus increasing the statistical power.

In the upcoming year, we plan to collect data from 10-15 more working groups, 5-10 more catalysis meetings, and 1 more hackathon. As a result, in the coming year, the "Science of Science" project will shift from data collection to data analysis. Hunter Jones (Master of Environmental Management student in the Nicholas School of the Environment) has been hired to continue the data collection where Chris Shields left off. In addition, we have posted a job opening for a Research Analyst to assist in the data analysis for the Science of Science project as well as assessment activities as a whole.

6.2 2012 Plans

In 2012, our assessment program is focusing on the sustainability of NESCent. We currently view our assessment program as having three main audiences including our current funders (NSF), future funders for sustainability of center, and internal scientists and staff for formative use of results to improve NESCent. Thus our assessment program should focus on function, productivity, and marketability. To achieve this, we have formed an assessment task force composed of the Directors, management team, and current assessment staff to coordinate our program to meet these three objectives.

In addition in Year 8, we plan to publish the results of our assessment program in the peer-reviewed literature. We think that many of the lessons we learned will be valuable to others, and also that our analyses will demonstrate the effectiveness of synthetic science. NESCent is also collaborating with Chaomei Chen (Drexel U.) on a Science of Science and Innovation Policy proposal to measure the intellectual variations and impact caused by new publications from NESCent and synthetic science.

7. Administration

The primary focus of the past year's activities within the administration at NESCent have been to increase efficiency, by building better tools and processes and by increasing staff training opportunities.

7.1 2011 Activities

Todd Vision, Assoc. Dir. for Informatics, will be on sabbatical from July 1, 2011 to June 30, 2012. During that time period, Hilmar Lapp served as Acting Associate Director from July 1, 2011 to August 31, 2011, and Joel Kingsolver, former Assoc. Dir. for Science, will be Acting Associate Director for Informatics from September 1, 2011 through June 2012. Joel is a faculty member in the Biology Department at The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill.

The administrative team provided their meeting planning expertise in helping prepare the NESCent-led bid to host Evolution 2014, coordinating a cooperative bid from Duke University, East Carolina University, North Carolina State University, the University of North Carolina at Greensboro and the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill.

The administrative team has developed a new Access driven database for use with logistics. The database has streamlined meeting preparation and communication with participants.

The administrative staff is also in the process of finalizing a Quickbooks-driven database for use in tracking programmatic expenses. While Duke University's SAP/R3 accounting system provides financial tracking, it is incapable of tracking expenditures on a programmatic level, for instance, tracking the costs of each individual meeting held at NESCent or the cost of other programs such as the Darwin Day Roadshow. Once completed, this database will provide a robust tool to manage and anticipate costs which will allow far more accurate monitoring of our programs.

Logistics staff attended the Meeting Planning International conference held at Durham, NC, in September 2011. Research Administration staff attended the North Carolina Society for Research Administrators meeting in Greensboro, NC in March, 2011. All staff are encouraged to take additional training that will increase efficiency and knowledge in support of NESCent programmatic activities.

7.1.1 Other Staff changes

Administrative

- Phillip Grosshans, Asst. Dir. for Research Administration, joined NESCent in Jan. 2011, replacing Karen Henry who retired in Dec. 2010. Phillip was formally an Assistant Director at Duke University's Office of Research Support.
- Lori Houjak joined NESCent as an Accounting Specialist in December 2010 replacing Julie McAlister.

Informatics

- Dave Clements, GMOD Help-desk, left NESCent in December 2010; hiring for a replacement is progressing through UNC-Chapel Hill.
- Xianhua Liu, Web Development Project Manager, left NESCent in January 2011; hiring for a replacement is progressing through UNC-Chapel Hill.

- Mattison Ward, Systems Administrator, joined NESCent in July 2011, replacing Jon Auman, who left in May 2011.

- Peter Midford, Research Scientist, joined NESCent in June 2011 after having previously served as a contractor to NESCent; he provides some support in replacing Kevin Clarke, Dryad Data Repository Programmer, who left NESCent in April 2011.

Education and Outreach

- Maryam Mohaghegh, Staff Specialist, joined NESCent as a part-time employee from May 2011 – Sept 2011.

7.1.2 Advisory Board

Tony Zera and Maureen Stanton left the NESCent Advisory Board after the February 2011 meeting. Fred Cohan, Troy Day, Maria Orive, and Cheryl Wilga end their terms on 30 Nov 2011. We have since recruited Weigang Qiu, Mark Stoneking and Ana Rivero; they began their 3-year terms on 1 Jul 2011. Vicki Funk and Carlo Maley will begin their terms on 1 Dec 2011.

7.1.3 Additional Space and Renovations

NESCent continues to grow, both in terms of its resident community of scientists, and in terms of the number of programs it supports. Consequently, there have been changes to NESCent's physical space. These include:

- Creation of a Visiting Scholar room to provide adequate space for our Short-term Visitors, Graduate Student Fellows and Journalists-in-Residence.
- New cubicle furniture was installed in the Informatics Room and the new Visiting Scholar Room of the main NESCent Erwin Mill building to provide more privacy and better working conditions for staff.

7.1.4 Information of Outside Services Agreements and Consultants

Consultants contracted during Year 7 were:

- AIBS for outreach at the NABT meeting and for development of new NESCent website;
- @Mire for Dryad development;
- Pegasus Info for Dryad planning and communication;
- Alpha Accounting for development of a shadow system to track expenditures by programmatic activities;
- Peter Midford for Phenoscape development and support of a NESCent working group; and
- Chris Mungall for Phenoscape development.

7.2 2012 Plans

NESCent staff have been informed about our plans for sustainability and the likelihood of various outcomes post-2014. Consequently, many staff are evaluating their career options. Our goal is to offer opportunities for staff development that complement their existing skills so that they are better able to serve NESCent as it expands into new areas, as well as enhancing their resumes for the future. One area that we see a need for at NESCent is facilitation training. A large fraction of NESCent's activities revolves around meetings and workshops. It makes sense to offer guidance on best practices associated with the development of meeting agendas, and with conducting the meetings themselves. This year, Craig McClain, NESCent's Assistant Director of Science, attended a facilitation certification course, and has expanded our best-practices guides to PIs. In 2012, we expect to send other key NESCent personnel for training in facilitation.

NESCent is located in a historic textile mill in a vibrant university community at the edge of the Duke University campus.

8. EXTERNALLY FUNDED RESEARCH: NESCent Grants and Proposals

Funded: NESCent–Duke University

TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
Show Me the Evolution! Assessing Effectiveness of a New Teaching Resource	Allen Rodrigo Kristin Jenkins	NSFI	1/1/2009– 12/31/2011	117,976	32,024	150,000
EAGER: NESCent Ambassador Program	Allen Rodrigo Jory Weintraub	NSF	5/1/2011– 4/30/2013	239,276	25,239	264,515
Evolutionary Analysis of the Histone Deacetylase Family: Biomedical Research	Allen Rodrigo (on behalf of NIH Senior Fellow Joseph Graves)	NIH	9/1/2011– 8/31/2013	121,924	–	121,924
Spanish-Language Translation of “Evolution in the News”	Allen Rodrigo Jory Weintraub	European Society for Evolutionary Biology	5/1/2011– 4/30/2012	3,500	–	3,500
ABI Innovation: A Novel Database and Ontology for Evolutionary Analysis of Mammalian Feeding Physiology	Hilmar Lapp (Chris Wall)	NSF (Subaward from Duke's Dept. of Evolutionary Anthropology)	7/1/2011– 6/30/2014	27,490	15,670	43,160
INTEROP: International Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences	Hilmar Lapp (William Michener)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of New Mexico)	5/15/2008– 6/30/2012	39,535	11,268	50,803
ABI Development: Ontology-Enabled Reasoning Across Phenotypes from Evolution and Model Organisms	Hilmar Lapp (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from UNC-Chapel Hill)	7/1/2011– 6/30/2015	Included under UNC Chapel Hill's prime award		748,394
Supplement: Supplement for NSF-EU Workshop in Brussels	Allen Rodrigo	NSF	7/25/2011– 11/30/2011	3,294	939	4,233
A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology	Todd Vision	NSF	9/1/2008– 8/31/2012	1,900,625	279,551	2,180,176
DataONE: Observation Network for Earth	Todd Vision (William Michener)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of New Mexico)	8/1/2009– 12/31/2011	111,182	31,686	142,868
Helping Interdisciplinary Vocabulary Engineering (HIVE)	Todd Vision	Institute for Museum & Library Science	1/1/2009– 6/30/2012	cost share only from Duke University		
The iPlant Collaborative	Todd Vision Karen Cranston	NSF (Subaward from Univ of Arizona)	10/1/10– 3/31/12	13,850	3,948	17,798
Supplement: Synthesizing Synthesis: Bringing Synthesis Centers Closer and Integrating Activities	Allen Rodrigo	NSF	12/1/2011– 11/30/2012	106,479	4,364	110,843
TOTAL DUKE FUNDED				2,685,131	404,689	3,838,214

8. EXTERNALLY FUNDED RESEARCH: NESCent Grants and Proposals

Funded: NESCent–University of North Carolina (UNC)

TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology	Jane Greenberg (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke Univ)	9/1/2008–8/31/2012	included under Duke Univ. prime award		365,525
Enhancement of the GBrowse Genome Annotation Browser	Todd Vision (Ian Holmes)	NIH (Subaward from Univ of California-Berkeley)	9/1/2007–8/31/2011	281,718	77,480	359,198
Linking Evolution to Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies	Todd Vision (Paula Mabee)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of South Dakota)	6/1/2007–8/31/2011	853,338	197,607	1,050,945
ABI Development: Ontology-Enabled Reasoning Across Phenotypes from Evolution and Model Organisms	Todd Vision (Paula Mabee)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of South Dakota)	7/1/2011–6/30/2015	1,127,219	178,572	1,305,791
The Hymenoptera Ontology: Part of a Transformation in Systemic and Genome Science	Tood Vision (Andy Deans)	NSF (Subaward from North Carolina State University)	9/1/2010–8/31/2011	65,946	18,465	84,411
TOTAL UNC FUNDED				2,328,221	472,124	3,165,870

Funded: NESCent–North Carolina State University (NCSU)

TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology	Kristin Antelman (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke Univ)	9/1/2008-8/31/2012	included under Duke Univ. prime award		134,686
Biological Collections Digitization: Towards Capture and Mobilization of Biodiversity Information Resources	Brian Wiegmann	NSF	4/21/10-4/20/11	35,951	2,518	38,469
CCLI Phase II: Extendig and Enhancing Understanding Evolution for the Undergraduate Community	Brian Wiegmann (Roy Caldwell)	NSF (Subaward from UC-Berkeley)	9/1/2009-8/31/2012	22,810	5,930	28,740
TOTAL NCSU FUNDED				58,761	8,448	201,895

8. EXTERNALLY FUNDED RESEARCH: NESCent Grants and Proposals

Pending: NESCent–Duke

TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
ABI Development: Towards a Comprehensive, Community-Owned and Sustainable Repository of Reuseable Phylogenetic Knowledge	Hilmar Lapp	NSF	1/1/2012–12/31/2014	1,015,275	241,390	1,256,665
Natural Trap Cave Revisited: Ancient DNA, Climate and the Megafuana Extinction	Julie Meachen-Samuels	NSF	6/1/2012–5/31/2014	249,941	113,687	363,628
ABI Development: Dryad: Scalable and Sustainable Infrastructure for the Publication of Data	Todd Vision	NSF	9/1/2012–8/31/2016	2,027,103	376,533	2,403,636
TOTAL DUKE PENDING				3,292,319	731,610	4,023,929

Pending: NESCent–UNC

TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
Enhancing the GMOD Suite of Genome Annotation and Visualization Tools	Todd Vision (Ian Holmes)	NIH (Subaward from Univ of California-Berkeley)	3/1/2011–2/29/2016	425,000	119,000	544,000
ABI Development: Dryad: Scalable and Sustainable Infrastructure for the Publication of Data	Jane Greenberg (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke University)	9/1/2012–8/31/2016	Included within Duke University's prime application		600,134
TOTAL UNC PENDING				425,000	119,000	1,144,134

Pending: NESCent–NCSU

TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
ABI Development: Dryad: Scalable and Sustainable Infrastructure for the Publication of Data	Kristin Antelman (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke University)	9/1/2012–8/31/2016	Included within Duke University's prime application		18,827
TOTAL NCSU PENDING						18,827

TOTAL FUNDED **5,957,374**

TOTAL PENDING **4,567,929**

TOTAL FUNDED AND PENDING **10,525,303**

For the full 2011 Annual Report and its Appendices, visit
http://www.nescent.org/AnnualReport_and_Appendices_Yr7.pdf